

Quartic Nonpolynomial Spline Solutions for Third Order Two-Point Boundary Value Problem

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Abstract—In this paper, we develop quartic nonpolynomial spline method for the numerical solution of third order two point boundary value problems. It is shown that the new method gives approximations, which are better than those produced by other spline methods. Convergence analysis of the method is discussed through standard procedures. Two numerical examples are given to illustrate the applicability and efficiency of the novel method.

Keywords—Quartic nonpolynomial spline, Two-point boundary value problem.

I. INTRODUCTION

WE consider the following third order two point boundary value problems

$$y^{(3)} + f(x)y = g(x), \quad x \in [a, b], \quad (1)$$

subject to the boundary conditions:

$$y(a) - A_1 = y^{(1)}(a) - A_2 = y^{(1)}(b) - A_3 = 0, \quad (2)$$

where $A_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ are finite real constants. The functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are continuous on the interval $[a, b]$.

The analytical solution of the problem (1-2) can not be obtained for arbitrary choices of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$.

The numerical analysis literature contains a few other methods developed to find an approximate solution of this problem. Al Said et al. [1] have solved a system of third order two point boundary value problems using cubic splines. Noor et al. [4] generated second order method based on quartic splines. Other authors [2,3] generated finite difference using fourth degree B-spline and quintic polynomial spline for this problem subject to other boundary conditions.

The aim of this paper is to construct a new spline method based on a nonpolynomial spline function that has a polynomial part and a trigonometric part to develop numerical methods for obtaining smooth approximations for the solution of the problem (1) subject to the boundary conditions (2). Recently, new methods based on a nonpolynomial spline function that has a polynomial part and a trigonometric part is used to develop numerical methods for obtaining numerical approximation for some partial differential equations, see for example [6,7]. An extension of the work of Ramadan et al

[5], we propose in this paper quartic nonpolynomial spline method for the numerical solution of third order two point boundary value problem (1-2).

The paper is organized as follows: In section II, we derive our method. The method is formulated in a matrix form in section III. Convergence analysis for our order methods is established in section IV. Numerical results are presented to illustrate the applicability and accuracy in section V. Finally, in section VI, we concluded the numerical results of the proposed methods.

II. DERIVATION OF THE METHOD

We introduce a finite set of grid points x_i by dividing the interval $[a, b]$ into $(n+1)$ equal parts where:

$$x_i = a + ih, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad x_0 = a, \quad x_n = b, \quad h = \frac{b-a}{n}. \quad (3)$$

Let $u(x)$ be the exact solution of the system (1-2) and S_i be an approximation to $u_i = u(x_i)$ obtained by the segment $Q_i(x)$ passing through the points (x_i, S_i) and (x_{i+1}, S_{i+1}) . Each nonpolynomial spline segment $Q_i(x)$ has the form:

$$Q_i(x) = a_i \cos k(x-x_i) + b_i \sin k(x-x_i) + c_i(x-x_i)^2 + d_i(x-x_i) + e_i, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

where a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i and e_i are constants and k is the frequency of the trigonometric functions which will be used to raise the accuracy of the method and Eq. (4) reduces to quartic polynomial spline function in $[a, b]$ when $k \rightarrow 0$.

First, we develop expressions for the six coefficients of (4) in terms of $S_i, S_{i+1}, D_i, D_{i+1}, F_i$, and F_{i+1} where

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & Q_i(x_i) = S_i, & Q_i(x_{i+1}) &= S_{i+1}, \\ (ii) \quad & Q_i^{(1)}(x_i) = D_i, & Q_i^{(1)}(x_{i+1}) &= D_{i+1}, \\ (iii) \quad & Q_i^{(3)}(x_i) = F_i, & Q_i^{(3)}(x_{i+1}) &= F_{i+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

We obtain via a straightforward calculation the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} a_i &= \frac{h^3}{\theta^3 \sin(\theta)} (F_{i+1} - F_i \cos(\theta)) & b_i &= -h^3 \frac{F_i}{\theta^3}, \\ c_i &= \frac{1}{h^2} (S_{i+1} - S_i) - \frac{h(\cos(\theta) - 1)}{\theta^3 \sin(\theta)} (F_{i+1} + F_i) - \frac{D_i}{h} - \frac{h}{\theta^2} F_i, \end{aligned}$$

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The analytical solution of (25) is:

$$y(x) = x(1-x)e^x. \quad (26)$$

The numerical results for our methods are summarized in Tables I-II and compared with other existing polynomial spline methods in Table III.

Tables I-II show the numerical results for a class of methods based on quartic nonpolynomial spline. These tables reveal that our methods have accurate results. While in Table III our methods are better than (in terms of accuracy) other methods (cubic and quartic spline methods).

VI. CONCLUSION

A class of methods is presented for solving third order two-point boundary value problem using quartic nonpolynomial spline. These methods are shown to be optimal second order, which are better than other methods. The obtained numerical results show that the proposed methods maintain a very remarkable high accuracy which make them are very encouraging for dealing with the solution of two-point boundary value problems.

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